

Recommended citation: Laperrouza, M., Aeberli, M., & Puissant, P. (2020). Developing a Self-Assessment Tool for Design-Driven Open-Ended Engineering Projects. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 926-936). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654115.

DEVELOPING A SELF-ASSESSMENT TOOL FOR ENGINEERING STUDENTS ENGAGED IN OPEN-ENDED PROJECTS WITH A HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN APPROACH

M. Laperrouza¹

College of Humanities, EPFL
Lausanne, Switzerland

M. Aeberli

College of Humanities, EPFL
Lausanne, Switzerland

P-X. Puissant

College of Humanities, EPFL
Lausanne, Switzerland

Topics (3): *Interdisciplinary education, Challenge based education, Maker projects*

Keywords (4): *design, open-ended projects, learning companion, self-assessment*

ABSTRACT

The paper presents an ongoing research project aimed at providing engineering students with a self-assessment tool when working on open-ended projects with a human-centered design approach. Based on our existing framework, we develop a tool aimed at alleviating some of the challenges experienced by students and faculty when running such projects. For instance, we have noticed that students face difficulties in framing problems, evaluating solutions or developing prototyping strategies. From a faculty perspective, it is not always easy to identify which students struggle with different phases specific to projects with a design approach and thus to provide the best possible support to students at the right moment. The tool offers a set of questions to assess students' progression and provides guidance to help in case of difficulty. Faculty can thus better allocate their time by focusing on those experiencing difficulties and ensure that those unaware of difficulties remain "on track".

¹ *Corresponding Author*
M. Laperrouza
marc.laperrouza@epfl.ch

1 RATIONALE AND PRELIMINARY RESEARCH

1.1 Rationale

In our experience, developing and running courses for open-ended projects with a human-centered design approach faces a number of structural challenges :

- Fit with the rigid and highly structured academic timeline, with a weekly structure and fixed assessment periods; for instance, not all teams progress at the same speed, or some teams undergo several iterations which can lead to teams being at different points of the process at a given time; this raises questions of facilitation (e.g., nature and frequency) and, more generally, of the logic of progression
- Alignment with an academic mission which tends to emphasize learning over result; this raises questions of assessment (e.g., tension between mastering the process and reaching an acceptable result)

These challenges echo findings from the literature on design thinking education in engineering schools. Dym & al. [3] have argued that teaching divergent inquiry in design thinking is neither recognized clearly nor performed well in engineering curricula. More precisely, they posit that “the real challenge is not the adoption of the principles of divergent-convergent inquiry; rather, it is the integration of divergent-convergent inquiry into the existing engineering curricula”.

On the same topic, Bennetts, Cheeley, Caldwell, & Green [1] find that students' ability in divergent thinking remains stagnant throughout their engineering degree. More recently, Coleman & al. [2] find that “the perceived design thinking ability of senior engineering students is significantly less than that of first-year students interested in engineering” and call for development of feedback seeking and experimentalism skills.

Retna [10] points to two other important issues: engineering students' inexperience in real life problems and research, and class size facilitation. While highlighting the value of design tools, Mosely & al. [9] point to issues of problem definition (e.g., difficulties in framing and reframing the project brief) and the experimentation and failure process during problem-solving. They also address the question of facilitators and their ability to provide guidance and feedback on the design process for non-design students.

In short, while developing competences to work on open-ended projects is broadly recognized as an important learning objective, it meets with challenges for both students and faculty members.

In light of the above, we wanted to capture in more detail the diversity of difficulties faced by engineering students at different moments of their project and propose a tool allowing them to assess their progression and, if necessary, help them overcome the difficulties in the form of questions.

1.2 Preliminary Research

We conducted a survey in 3 different EPFL courses consisting of semester-long open-ended team projects with a human-centered design approach. Teams were introduced to the way we, in our methodology, differentiate 3 main phases in open-ended projects (as described in the “Framework” part), and were asked to list the difficulties encountered in the different phases of the process. The survey was conducted at the end of the process, allowing for reflexive feedback. It targeted the phases of the process experienced by the students in their respective course. Table 1 provides the results of this survey, later referred to as “test 1”.

Table 1. Difficulties faced by students in design-driven open-ended projects

Verified		Discovered	
RESEARCH : Explore (n=6)			
We didn't know how to proceed	50%	The topic was not framed well	16%
We didn't know which field(s) to investigate	50%	We were divided on which topic to explore	16%
...	< 50%		
RESEARCH : Define (n=6)			
We didn't know if our opportunity was relevant	66%	We didn't know if our opportunity was yet addressed	16%
We didn't know if we had enough data	50%	We didn't know how to formulate our opportunity	16%
...	< 50%		
IDEATION : Generate (n=15)			
We didn't know if our ideas were good or bad	60%	We put too many constraints on ourselves	21%
The constraints limited our ideas	53%	We struggled finding new ideas	13%
...	< 50%		
IDEATION : Select (n=15)			
We didn't know on which criteria we should base our choice	40%	We didn't know if our solution was realistic	27%
We had to mix 2 or more solutions	33%	Constraints forced us to choose a specific solution	13%
...	< 30%		
PROTOTYPING : Build (n=13)			
We didn't know how finished our prototype was supposed to be	70%	We encountered technical difficulties	23%
We didn't have the skills to build it	38%	We had internal team issues	23%
...	< 35%	...	< 10%
PROTOTYPING : Test (n=11)			
We had no testing strategy	27%	...	< 10%
We didn't know how to run tests	27%		
...	< 20%		

Source: compiled by authors

All of the pre-identified difficulties were confirmed. New ones were also identified, highlighting how different the experience can be when confronted with the same process.

Some of the difficulties confirm earlier literature findings, such as the importance of setting the right amount of constraints [4], echoing the tension between the need for structure and the freedom required by open-ended projects. Most difficulties faced by the students, however, fall under a “how-to” umbrella, illustrating a lack of methodological know-how from students when exposed to such processes, particularly in the first steps of the process (i.e. the Research and Ideation phases). This echoes our experience: the need for methodological mentoring becomes decreasingly important as the students evolve through the different phases. While crucial in the phases which engineering students are the least familiar with, it is less important in the “hands-on” phases (i.e., Prototyping). Also, the more students take ownership of the process, the less mentoring is needed.

Some of the difficulties highlighted also confirm what is identified in the literature as the “exit dilemma” [7]: being uncomfortable when relying on soft skills, dealing with ambiguity [5] and solving real-life problems [10]. It remains hard for students to measure what is the right amount of try, fail, and the quality of their outcomes in regard of the tension between the exploratory nature of their projects and the academic timeline.

The existing literature, coupled with our experience and survey findings, comforted us in the need to develop a tool aimed at alleviating some of these issues.

2 PRESENTATION OF THE FRAMEWORK AND THE TOOL

2.1 The Framework

We conceptualized our self-assessment tool on the basis of a framework that we developed and refined over the years through a number of courses conducted at EPFL. The framework takes its inspiration from a number of approaches developed since the mid 90's (e.g., British Council, IDEO). At the core of these approaches, one can usually find such concepts as convergence and divergence, iteration and human-centered design.

Fig. 1. RIP Framework

Our framework attempts to cater as much as possible to an academic context. For instance, emphasis is placed on process modularity to take into account the diversity of course formats and learning outcomes. In certain cases, a project brief is already defined (e.g., given by an industrial partner). In other cases, there is no project brief and students have to start from a white sheet of paper. At EPFL, many open-ended courses tend to start either at the Ideation phase, or at the Prototyping phase. In other words, the brief is already given, in a more or less framed state, but very little if no time is usually dedicated to research and the proper “building” of this brief with students. At times, faculty wants to emphasize process (whatever the result); at times, it prefers to ensure a certain quality in the result (e.g., in the case of service design or field intervention) or encourage technical innovation over market demand. Moreover, some projects run over a week (e.g., block module) while others can last several semesters (e.g. a minor or a competition).

2.2 The Self-Assessment Tool

The proposed self assessment tool is designed as a digital mediator whose goal is to unload the weight of automatisable interactions off the shoulders of the facilitator by providing students with essential support during open-ended projects with a human-centered design approach. It should therefore allow for better and more targeted interactions with the students requiring help.

The tool was developed with a number of different pedagogical scenarios in mind :

- Semester or multi-semester course: a more traditional approach fitting into the regular academic calendar
- Stand-alone project: students are increasingly participating in “practical” projects (either credited or non-credited, supervised or unsupervised)

- Design sprints: as schools develop new teaching formats, some favor block formats where students focus their energy on a single project for a limited amount of time

In its current implementation state, the tool works as follows: in a dedicated interface, the facilitator first sets up its course, that students can then enroll in. He sets which phase among Research, Ideation and Prototyping will be covered by the project (at least one, and if only 2, they must be consecutive).

The student then opens the self-assessment tool and enrolls in the corresponding course. Building on literature's statement [6] that formulating questions is a best practice in design-driven open-ended teaching, the tool then offers the student a sequence of questionnaires, each corresponding to one of the phases covered by the course. When the student wants to assess progress over a specific phase, he takes the corresponding questionnaire. One cannot bypass a phase as a phase needs to be validated before proceeding to the next one.

Each phase's questionnaire is designed as a series of 3 to 4 questions targeting key-elements of the phase, inviting the student to reflect on his progress. A set of 8 potential answers is proposed, covering situations the student might identify with.

After the questionnaire, a comprehensive diagnosis highlights the results of the student in each key aspect of the phase and proposes tailored advices and reflexive questions, inviting the student to evaluate the quality of his work. Also, he's provided with a reality check on whether he can proceed to the next phase or not on the basis of the results. It prevents students from moving on to the next phase too quickly - which is a natural tendency in such contexts [5].

In open-ended projects, constraints, success criteria, and failure should be clearly outlined [8], something even truer as the mediation becomes digital. Therefore, questions, answers and feedback are designed to be comprehensive, yet straightforward.

This self-assessment should allow the student to reflect on his work. At the same time, the backend of the tool allows the facilitator to oversee the progression of the students and identify pain points: this should allow to better tailor what resources to provide & time to allocate for specific "debugging" with teams in need.

3 EARLY VALIDATION PROCESS AND FINDINGS

3.1 Early Validation Process

As a first step, the validation process of the self-assessment tool targeted the understandability, the relevance and the usefulness of its components - namely questions, proposed answers, diagnosis and advice. While still technically in a beta version, we recently reached a point where it became possible to test some of its key aspects.

We took the case of a social innovation program we run in India to present the participants with this early version of the tool and gather feedback. The setup is one of the typical use cases of our tool: 10 students were engaged in a 2-week design research process covering Research, Ideation and Prototyping. Students are split in 3 teams, each working on a different design brief. In addition, students come from 3 different backgrounds: engineering (various fields), business and design. Each team is composed of students of at least 2 different backgrounds.

We first introduced the students to our framework, then to the beta version of the tool. Both the work-in-progress nature of the tool and the goal of the test was explained to the students. Individually, they were asked to use the tool one time per phase of the process. Each time, they were then asked to provide anonymous feedback on the segment of the tool they just used.

Table 2 provides this feedback (hereinafter referred to as “test 2”).

Table 2. Self-assessment tool testing feedback

RESEARCH (n=7)				
QUESTIONS	Understandability	Relevancy	Understandability	Variety
Topic	71,4%	100%	85,7%	14,3%
Exploration	85,7%	85,7%	100%	42,9%
Interpretation	100%	100%	100%	57,1
Problem	100%	100%	85,7%	71,4%
DIAG. & AD.	Understandability	Usefulness	Understandability	Usefulness
	100%	85,7%	100%	85,7%
IDEATION (n=3)				
QUESTIONS	Understandability	Relevancy	Understandability	Variety
Ideas	100%	100%	100%	100%
Sorting	100%	100%	100%	66,7%
Solution	100%	100%	100%	100%
DIAG. & AD.	Understandability	Usefulness	Understandability	Usefulness
	100%	100%	100%	100%
PROTOTYPING (n=0)				
QUESTIONS	Understandability	Relevancy	Understandability	Variety
Criteria	-	-	-	-
Prototype	-	-	-	-
Testing	-	-	-	-
Validation	-	-	-	-
DIAG. & AD.	Understandability	Usefulness	Understandability	Usefulness
	-	-	-	-

Source: compiled by authors

First, we can see that student feedback participation dramatically decreased over time. Following in person discussions with students, the decrease can be attributed to 2 reasons:

- The logic, structure and wording of the tool barely varies along the 3 phases. Students therefore considered that their feedback on any of the phases wouldn't change much.
- As the process unfolded, pressure in delivering the final outcomes of the program increased and didn't allow time for reflexive feedback on the tool.

Based on the above results, and keeping in mind the small sample, one can see that the wording of the tool is by-and-large understandable. Given the goal of the tool, the questions appear mostly relevant and the diagnosis and advice delivered by the tool feel mostly useful. However, one can see that the proposed answers don't come across as varied enough.

These results were confirmed by direct feedback: students that answered “no” to any of the above questions were asked to explain why, and to provide suggestions for improvement. Overall, the feedback fell into 3 main categories:

- Lack of diversity and details of the proposed answers: multiple comments pointed out that the proposed answers didn't represent the spectrum of the different difficulties faced by students during the process, and therefore didn't match their experience. In addition with the impossibility to provide further details or to add nuance, students provide the answer that they feel matches their experience the most, which is the “least bad”, and they can therefore feel a mismatch between the diagnosis provided and their experience. In particular, it was mentioned that the ratio of affirmative and negative answers should be more balanced. Suggestions were made to switch questions to answer to, to affirmations to relate to, and answers to a 1-10 scale.
- Interdependencies: one comment pointed out that the tool should count specific answers as red flags, and that the phase diagnosis shouldn't be a simple average of the results of the questions: it shouldn't be possible to consider a phase validated if something went wrong in the first steps. While this is the mechanic of the tool between the 3 main phases, this suggests to also implement it inside the phases.
- Lack of clarity: while the wording was considered clear, some comments pointed out the lack of clarity of the concepts underlying the tool. Specific vocabulary should be thoroughly explained in order to leave no ambiguity (e.g., by adding examples). Furthermore, comments pointed to the need of explaining the underlying framework.

3.2 Discussion of Findings

We identified 2 biases in test 2:

- As this program was coordinated by us, it was built following our framework. When students used the tool and provided feedback, they were therefore already familiar with the underlying concepts and the specific glossary we had introduced in the course. This leads to temper the feedback: as the tool is intended to be used across the institution, but not all design driven open-ended projects courses in the institution embrace our framework, this setting is unique.
- As the process was unfolding over the short program, time became scarcer and pressure grew. Students had more time and reflection to allocate to the testing and feedback of the tool in their project's Research phase, and less so in the other phases. This is verified by comments such as “same as for the Research phase” in the Ideation and Prototyping phase, leading to consider the Ideation phase feedback as more trustworthy.

While literature [6] suggests that formulating questions is a best practice in open-ended teaching and results from our test confirm this statement, we observed that in

the case of multiple-choice questions, they should be linked with meaningful answers that match students' experience. If not, it can make it hard for students to answer, knowing that their answer will not match the nuance of their experience. Proposed answers should thus reflect this nuance in order for students to be able to truly answer the question. Students might otherwise feel like any of the resulting diagnosis is not trustworthy or applicable.

Surprisingly, we can see that the diagnosis and advice were mostly rated as understandable and useful. As we knew that the proposed answers to our questions were narrow and didn't allow for nuances, we designed the diagnosis and advice to be as comprehensive as possible. This might be a way to overcome the lack of granularity of the answers, but won't change the students potential mistrust in diagnosis resulting from an answer not truly reflecting their experience, which is likely to vary a lot, as highlighted by the great variety of the difficulties faced by students reported in test 1.

4 FUTURE STEPS

The deployment of the first version of the self-assessment tool throughout the institution is envisaged over the coming semester, and upcoming developments shall build on the 3 main aspects of the findings. While the use of the framework "in presence" has shown positive results in terms of structuring our courses and guiding students through the different phases, one will need to verify whether the self-assessment tool "at a distance" manages similar results. For instance, it will be important to test whether the generic advice provided by the tool can replace more targeted advice provided by faculty. One will also need to ensure that the students answer "honestly" the questions and act upon the advice. More broadly, one will need to find the right rhythm for the coverage of theoretical aspects in each phase, the use of the self-assessment tool and facilitation about the project so that the students adopt the tool as an integral part of their learning journey.

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